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Extinction of Prepositions Since the Late Qing Dynasty

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ABSTRACT

Most of the extinction prepositions since the late Qing Dynasty are classical Chinese prepositions, including: spatio-temporal meanings, such as “迨(dài), 迨至(dàizhì), 迨及(dàijí), 俟(sì), 待(dài), 去(qù), 捱(ái), 望(wàng)” ; core meanings, such as “合(hé), 共(gòng), 教(jiào), 吃(chī), 捱(ái)” ; relational concepts, such as “照依(zhàoyī), 缘(yuán)”. These classical Chinese prepositions with unique written stylistic effect, either because of their verb meaning retention, or the new prepositions, or the economic principles of language have not survive in the contemporary Chinese preposition system.

INTRODUCTION

Since the late Qing Dynasty, Chinese prepositional system has been constantly adjusted and updated. The prepositional members of the same semantic subsystem, including new and non new prepositions, have been used in ancient Chinese, middle ancient Chinese and modern Chinese. But in the late Qing, or modern Chinese or contemporary Chinese, it disappeared, forming the replacement and extinction of prepositional members. Replace is a typical phenomenon in the process of grammaticalization. It is an alternative way to promote prepositions to approximately express the same thing. The new form does not directly replace the old one, but the competition between them promotes the extinction or loss of the old form. Therefore, replacement is the production of new quality elements, and the old ones are gradually disappearing. Finally, the new quality elements replace the old ones. In Chinese prepositional system, prepositional members have a large number of similar introduction functions. The rise of one party may lead to the disappearance or extinction of the other party. Similarly, the disappearance of one party will lead to the rise of the other party, which is the process of replacement and extinction.

Modern Chinese prepositional system is the continuation of ancient Chinese, but the vernacular expression structure leads to a large number of new prepositions, and the change of prepositions promotes the development of prepositional system. This development is manifested in the extinction of a large number of prepositions in classical Chinese, such as “迨/眾/逕(dài)”, “俟(sì)”.

The purpose of this paper is to sort out the extinction prepositions, analyze the reasons for the demise of prepositions as well as outline the development and evolution of Chinese prepositions and construct the system of extinct prepositions since the late Qing, and deepen the understanding of the development history of Chinese preposition system.

JUDGEMENT OF CHINESE PREPOSITION

From the perspective of linguistic typology, prepositions can be divided into prepositions and postpositions according to the standard of their positions. Greenberg (2010) proposed that

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prepositions also include frame prepositions and argued that besides prepositions and postpositions, ambiposition can also be prepositions^[5].

Chinese prepositions usually refer to prepositions. The prepositions discussed in this paper are limited to prepositions. Because the frame preposition is produced by the co-occurrence of preposition and postposition or other words, it is not a fixed term. Therefore, we only deal with this syntactic phenomenon and do not treat it as a word. So how to judge prepositions? Chinese prepositions are basically derived from the grammaticalization of verbs. In theory, prepositions can be judged on the basis of the comparison of similarities and differences between verb and preposition. Based on the opinions of different scholars, we propose a method to determine prepositions.

- (1) Syntactic position: the syntactic basis of verb preposition process is the V1 position of "V1· N· V2".
- (2) Syntactic function: whether it can be used as predicate component in clause alone. A verb can be used as a predicate component to form an independent expression structure; a preposition cannot, but must have an object, and the prepositional structure cannot form an independent expression structure.
- (3) Semantic empty and real: verb meaning is real, including action meaning; preposition meaning becomes empty, action meaning disappears, and relevant semantic components are introduced to v2;
- (4) Morphological differences: verbs can be marked with aspect, such as "着(zhe)" "了(le)" "过(guò)", while prepositions can't.

DIVISION OF PREPOSITION SEMANTIC SYSTEM

Traditionally, the semantic classification of Chinese prepositions includes: the category of time and place, including the semantic components of time, place and direction; the category of object and scope: the sub semantic components such as the object, relation, exclusion, coordination etc.; the category of way, conditional and basis; the category of cause and purpose. This kind of classification treated the status of prepositions flatly and classified according to the semantic category of prepositional object; and the semantic relationship between prepositional structure and verb is not prominent. Hence, this paper adopts the preposition semantic classification system of Hagège (2010:261-264)^[3], and the semantic system of prepositions since the late Qing Dynasty is divided into three major semantic domains: spatial-temporal meanings, core meanings and relational concepts. Each semantic domain has its own sub semantic types.

Prepositions with spatial-temporal meanings represent the spatial-temporal relationship, including spatial domain and temporal domain meanings. They can be subdivided into semantic components such as beginning, place, destination, direction, passage, approach, distance, opportunity and so on. Prepositions with core meanings mainly express the argument relationship with action behavior, which is also called actancy meaning. It mainly involves the grammatical functions of subject, object and indirect object and introduces agent, patient and possessive markers respectively (Hagège, 2010:273; 283)^[3]. The core meaning domain of this study includes agent, patient, object (such as expression, coordination, comparison, benefit, etc.) and other semantic components. The prepositions with relational concepts mainly express the non argument relationship with action behavior, including exclusive, comitative, instrumentive, mediative, motivative, purposive and comparative (Hagège, 2010:261-264)^[3]. We divide the semantic roles within the relational concepts domain into: dependence and means (including tools, means, conditions, methods, basis and other sub components), cause and purpose, and involved scope and other sub domains.

Additionally, this paper selects some representative literary works from the late Qing Dynasty to the present, and the CCL modern Chinese corpus of Peking University Chinese Linguistics Research Center (http://ccl.pku.edu.cn:8080/ccl_Corpus/) as the main reference corpus.

PREPOSITION MEMBERS IN THE YUAN, MING AND QING DYNASTY

The diachronic comparison of Chinese prepositional system is through comparison between the later generation and the former one: the Han Dynasty is compared with the pre-Qin Dynasty, the Wei and

Jin Dynasties are compared with the two Han Dynasties, the Sui and Tang Dynasties are compared with the Wei and Jin Dynasties, and the Song, Yuan and Ming dynasties are compared with the Sui and Tang Dynasties. But this paper obviously can't be written from the ancient to the present. From the perspective of inheritance and development, this paper makes comparison with the previous period: Yuan, Ming and early Qing Dynasty. The prepositional system of the previous period is used as a coordinate to investigate the prepositions disappeared in this period.

Prepositions Continuously Used

There are 92 prepositions used in the early Yuan, Ming and Qing Dynasties, including (1) 27 in the pre Qin period, (2) 21 in the Han Dynasty, (3) 18 in the Wei and Jin Dynasties, (4) 18 in the Sui and Tang Dynasties, and (5) 8 in the Song Dynasty. For example:

- (1) 比(bǐ) 当(dāng) 到(dào) 暨(jì) 假(jiǎ) 向(xiàng) 沿(yán) 由(yóu) 自(zì)
- (2) 按(àn) 对(duì) 共(gòng) 将(jiāng) 竟(jìng) 涉(shè) 随(suí) 遭(zāo) 值(zhí) 坐(zuò)
- (3) 傍(bàng) 趁(chèn) 经(jīng) 就(jiù) 凭(píng) 替(tì) 同(tóng) 问(wèn) 仗(zhàng) 著(zhe)
- (4) 把(bǎ) 吃(chī) 拦(lán) 论(lùn) 去(qù) 似(sì) 捉(zhuō) 除非(chúfēi)
- (5) 朝(cháo) 倚(yǐ) 趁着(chènzhe) 打从(dǎcóng) 因为(yīnwèi)

New Prepositions

There are 52 new prepositions in the Yuan, Ming and Qing Dynasties, including: (1) 25 in the Yuan and Ming Dynasties, including 8 monosyllabic and 17 disyllabic; (2) 27 in the Qing Dynasty, including 5 monosyllabic and 22 disyllabic prepositions. For example:

- (1) 奔(bèn) 赶(gǎn) 借(jiè) 离(lí) 俟(sì) 赶趁(gǎnchèn) 投得(tóude) 投至到(tóuzhìdào) 一投(yītóu) 依仗(yīzhàng) 因着(yīnzhe) 遵依(zūnyī)
- (2) 挨(āi) 捱(ái) 朝了(cháole) 当着(dāngzhe) 对着(duizhe) 靠着(kàozhe) 临着(línzhe) 顺着(shùnzhe) 为了(wèile) 向着(xiàngzhe) 由着(yóuzhe) 照着(zhàozhe)

In the Yuan, Ming and Qing Dynasties, there are 61 extinction prepositions compared with the previous generation; there are 144 prepositions, of which 92 continuously used; 52 new prepositions.

Preposition Members Extincted in This Period

The preposition members in Yuan, Ming and early Qing Dynasties, except those extincted in the middle of Qing Dynasty, there are two types of prepositional members that have extincted since the late Qing: completely disappeared and basically extincted.

1. Completely extincted preposition

There are 9 prepositional members that have disappeared completely, including “去(qù), 望(wàng), 合(hé), 共(gòng), 教(jiào), 吃(chī), 照依(zhàoyī), 缘(yuán)” and “捱(ái)”.

2. Basically extincted preposition

The basic extincted preposition means that such prepositions are rarely seen. There are six such prepositions, including “迨(dài), 迨至(dàizhì), 迨及(dàijí), 俟(sì), 待(dài)”, and “捱(ái)” with passive meaning. Among them, “迨(dài), 迨至(dàizhì), 迨及(dàijí), 俟(sì)” are traditional prepositions, basic extincted in modern Chinese and only occasionally used in the expression of classical Chinese.

To sum up, the composition of prepositions that disappeared since the late Qing is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of Prepositions Extincted Since the Late Qing Dynasty

Meaning domain	Spatial-temporal meanings	Core meanings	Relational concepts
Preposition member	<u>迨(dài)</u> 迨至(dàizhì), <u>迨及(dàiji)</u> 俟(sì) <u>待(dài)</u> 去(qù) <u>望(wàng)</u>	合(hé) 共(gòng) 教(jiào) 吃(chī) 捱(ái)	照依(zhàoyī)

(Note: the underlined prepositions refer to the basically extinct prepositions, and the rest are completely extinct ones)

DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF NEW PREPOSITIONS

The new prepositions are in a dynamic development process and keep competing with the original preposition system members. The result of competition is that the central member status of preposition system is the most stable and lasts for the longest time. The farther away from the center, the more unstable the preposition status is, and the more likely it will be eliminated from the preposition system. Each preposition has activity. In the process of development, there may be two kinds of development results: possible existence or possible extinction.

Possible Extinction

Chinese new prepositions, from germination to development, to extinction, become meteor prepositions, that is, verbs become empty prepositions and then disappear, just as meteor rises or falls, terminating the use of prepositions, it will inevitably go through a period of time, even a long process.

From the late Qing to the present, the development of Chinese prepositional system in the late modern and modern times has been approaching maturity, and the internal changes are small. Therefore, we can only talk about which new prepositions will evolve into meteor prepositions from the perspective of prediction. Meteor preposition returns to the original verb and stops grammaticalization. Generally speaking, limited prepositions are grammaticalized with the limitation of verbs, which leads to the extremely limited semantic range of objects. Additionally, the competition for activity among members of Chinese prepositional system and the evolution of lexical semantic system are likely to withdraw from the preposition system. For example:

“赶到(gǎndào)” refers to the semantic component of the end of time, indicating that the usage of waiting for a certain time may die out in the future. The reasons are as follows: (1) the verb character of “arrive at” is strong; (2) it is faced with the competition of prepositions such as “等(děng), 到(dào), 等到(děngdào), 待(dài)”; (3) the scope of application is relatively small, which generally appears in Northern dialects.

“管(guǎn)”, to introduce the named object, may be replaced by the more mature preposition “把(bǎ)”. The reasons are as follows: (1) limited prepositions, prepositions and objects are limited to people, objects and events; (2) the scope of application is relatively narrow, only found in the Northeast Mandarin and Beijing dialect, but not in Mandarin; (3) the semantic meaning has not been completely bleached. Semantic bleaching refers to desemantization, that is, the disappearance (or generalization) of meaning content^{[1][2]} (Heine et al., 1991; Heine & Kuteva, 2007: 33-34). The process of verb’s grammaticalization into preposition is the process of losing the meaning of verb and converting it into the meaning of introduce. The verb function is still prominent, retaining seven verb meanings and usages (Modern Chinese dictionary, 6th Edition, page 480).

“除掉(chúdiào)” refers to the core meaning domain, indicating that the usage of semantic components of excluded objects may fade away. The verb meaning of “除掉(chúdiào)” is strong. The verb use case is far more than the preposition use case, forming the coexistence stage in the grammaticalization process (Hopper & Traugott, 1993:36). Besides, the semantic component of exclusion has the developed matured and existential preposition “除(chú)” and “除了(chúle)”.

Causes of the Extinction of Prepositions

1. Retention of verb meaning

Prepositions are used to mark certain semantic and grammatical functions. The higher the degree of grammaticalization, the stronger the functional stability. After grammaticalization, a verb may through the stage from less grammaticalization to more grammaticalization (Kurylowicz, 1965:69)^[7] and can be completely bleached, even become pure prepositions. Pure preposition words have the highest degree of grammaticalization (Hopper & Traugott, 1993)^[6]. Some prepositions in this process, due to the retention of verb meaning, their preposition meaning stability is not strong enough. It often stops at a certain stage of grammaticalization and does not develop into semi prepositions, or pure prepositions, or even gradually replaced by the passive meaning of words. The meaning of prepositions gradually declines and eventually dies out.

For example, “教(jiào)” has disposal and passive meaning. The preposition “教(jiào)” was born in the Tang Dynasty, and then developed very slowly; it was still rare in Song and Yuan Dynasties, more common in Ming Dynasty, and gradually disappeared after the late Qing Dynasty. In addition to the competition of new prepositions, it also comes from its strong verb nature and low grammaticalization. The original meaning of “教(jiào)” is educate and guide, which is still its main meaning.

2. Competition of synonymous prepositions

There is competition among synonymous prepositions in prepositional system. Some prepositions are produced early, but the competitiveness of the new prepositions is stronger than that of the new prepositions, thus crowding out the living space of the original prepositions. The emergence of “俟(sì)” and “待(dài)” appeared in the pre Qin period, but “俟(sì)” began to decline in the early Han Dynasty. Assuming that the total space in each semantic system is limited, then the decline of one side will inevitably give the other party more space for survival and development. Then, “待(dài)” began to occupy the mainstream position, and lasted until the Tang and Song dynasties. Another preposition “等(děng)” was born in the Song Dynasty and began to compete with “待(dài)”. After several hundred years of fierce competition, “等(děng)” finally replaced “待(dài)” in spoken Chinese.

3. Economic principles of language

The replacement relationship between “教(jiào)” and “叫(jiào)” lies in the principle of language economy. On the premise of ensuring smooth communication, users of language symbols strive to pay attention to the principle of efficiency, economy and labor saving. That is to say, in verbal communication, people always use the least input to get the maximum communication effect, which is the principle of language economy. The confusion of pronunciation and meaning between “教(jiào)” and “叫(jiào)” is a communicative burden, and the language itself will adjust. Compared with “教(jiào)”, “叫(jiào)” is more in line with the law of cognition and semantic grammaticalization, and the path is simpler. Because the passive expression comes from the external agent, it is decided that “叫(jiào)” is more powerful than “教(jiào)”, so “教(jiào)” has become one of the vanishing parties.

Based on the principle of language economy, there is redundancy between “照依(zhàoyī)” and “依照(yīzhào)”. “照依(zhàoyī)” is prior to “依照(yīzhào)”. “照依(zhàoyī)” was first seen in Song Dynasty and developed slowly until Ming Dynasty, and then declined gradually after Qing Dynasty. “依照(yīzhào)” came into being after the May 4th Movement. In the late Qing, the preposition “按照(ànzhào)、遵照(zūnzhào)” was born. Therefore, “依照(yīzhào)” was more in line with the speaker's language use psychology than “照依(zhàoyī)”, and “照依(zhàoyī)” finally extincted from the preposition system.

Law of Extinction

1. Regression of verb usage

Grammaticalization is a process in which a notional word or structure in a certain context is used to the grammatical elements of idioms and continue to develop grammatical functions (Kurylowicz, 1965:5)^[7]. Talmy (1979:209) noted that the stage of grammaticalization is discourse > syntax > morphology > phoneme > zero form^[4]. Hopper and Traugott (1993:7) believed that the cline of grammaticalization is: substantive word > grammatical word > attachment word > inflectional affix, and it has irreversible unidirectionality, that is, downgrading from left to right, but not upgrading from right to left^[6]. Auwera (2002:19-30) and Norde (2009:256) questioned this and demonstrated the degrammaticalization along the reverse evolution of the continuum from right to left^{[8][9]}. Chinese prepositions are basically derived from verbs, but many verbs do not follow the grammaticalization slope to the end, some stop at a certain stage; some stop grammaticalization, withdraw prepositions and return to verbs. For example, “去(qù), 望(wàng), 教(jiào), 吃(chī)” were grammaticalized into prepositions, but they did not maintain or continue to grammaticalize, but return to verbs, which are still used today.

2. Prepositions in classical Chinese are easier to disappear

Modern and contemporary written vernacular Chinese tends to colloquial prepositions, and eliminates written prepositions. Classical Chinese prepositions have a strong color in written language, so they are easier to disappear. Such as “迨/逮/選(dài), 俟(sì)” etc..

3. Gradual extinction

In each era of the history of Chinese language development, there are some new qualitative elements emerging and the old ones disappearing gradually. The disappearance of prepositions is also a gradual process. For example, the words “迨(dài), 迨至(dàizhì), 迨及(dàijí), 俟(sì), 待(dài)”, after modern, modern and contemporary Chinese, they have not completely extincted.

CONCLUSION

This chapter summarizes the prepositions that have disappeared since the late Qing Dynasty, and most of them are classical Chinese prepositions, including spatio-temporal meanings, such as “迨(dài), 迨至(dàizhì), 迨及(dàijí), 俟(sì), 待(dài), 去(qù), 捱(ái), 望(wàng)”; core meanings, such as “合(hé), 共(gòng), 教(jiào), 吃(chī), 捱(ái)”; relational concepts, such as “照依(zhàoyī), 缘(yuán)”. Among them, “迨(dài), 迨至(dàizhì), 迨及(dàijí), 俟(sì), 待(dài), 捱(ái)” almost extincted, the rest extincted completely. The extinction of classical prepositions in modern and contemporary Chinese has a unique stylistic effect. But in general, Chinese is easier to speak and understand. Additionally, the prepositions themselves have more verb meanings, the fierce competition among the members of the preposition system and the economic principles of language and other factors make these classical Chinese prepositions may be replaced by existential prepositions with strong vitality, or even new prepositions appear.

The emergence of new Chinese prepositions and the extinction of original prepositions are the performance of continuous optimization and updating of Chinese preposition system, which will inevitably go through a period of time. New Chinese Prepositions are deeply influenced by social environment. After the late Qing, Chinese society experienced great changes, especially after the May 4th Movement, Chinese native language changed from classical Chinese to vernacular. Chinese culture was deeply influenced by western culture, and language contact had an impact on Chinese preposition system. There are two choices for new Chinese prepositions: they may exist or they may die out. Since the late Qing Dynasty, less than 200 years, the new prepositions are still in the process of development, some of them with vitality can survive to this day; the other part of them may gradually be marginalized or even disappear in a certain development stage, and finally quit the Chinese preposition system.

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